

THE TAXONOMIC INTERPRETATION OF VISUAL COGNITIVE VERBS

Karimjonova Shahlo Ravshanjonovna

*Fergana State University Department of Practical English Course
Senior Lecturer (PhD)*

E-mail: shahloxonkarimjonova@gmail.com

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Abstract. *This article explores visual perception verbs in English and Uzbek from a cognitive-linguistic perspective. Special attention is given to the semantic and grammatical characteristics of verbs such as to see, to look, ko'ymoq, and qaramoq, which are classified using Y.V. Paducheva's taxonomic approach (T-categories). The study also applies N.N. Boldyrev's conceptual-taxonomic analysis, allowing for the identification of the hierarchical structure of the "visual perception" concept. The article outlines both obligatory and optional features of the concept, along with different levels and layers of the perception verb taxonomy. The comparative analysis reveals both similarities and differences in how visual perception verbs are expressed in English and Uzbek. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the relationship between linguistic units and cognitive structures.*

Key words: *visual perception, verb taxonomy, T-categories, semantics, cognitive linguistics, perception verbs, conceptual analysis, English and Uzbek, propositional structure, active/passive perception.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi vizual idrok fe'llari kognitiv-lingvistik jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Fe'llarning semantik va grammatik xususiyatlari Y.V.Paducheva tomonidan taklif etilgan taksonomik (T-kategoriya) yondashuv asosida ko'rib chiqiladi. Mazkur yondashuv doirasida vizual idrokni ifodalovchi "to see", "to look", "ko'ymoq", "qaramoq" kabi fe'llar faol va passiv idrok farqlari asosida guruhlariga ajratiladi. Shuningdek, N.N. Boldyrev tomonidan ilgari surilgan konseptual-taksonomik tahlil metodi asosida vizual idrok konseptining propozitsional tuzilmasi va iyerarxik darajalari aniqlanadi. Maqolada o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi vizual idrok fe'llarining kognitiv xususiyatlari, leksik realizatsiyasi va iyerarxik tasnifi asosida ularning umumiy va farqli jihatlari ochib beriladi. Tadqiqot til birliklari va idrok konseptining murakkab munosabatlarini aniqlash, ularni tilshunoslik va kognitiv sohalarida chuqurroq o'rganish imkonini beradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *vizual idrok, fe'llar taksonomiyasi, T-kategoriyalar, semantika, kognitiv lingvistika, perception verbs, konseptual tahlil, ingliz va o'zbek tili, propozitsional tuzilma, faol/passiv idrok.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются глаголы визуального восприятия в английском и узбекском языках с точки зрения когнитивной лингвистики. Особое внимание уделяется семантическим и грамматическим особенностям таких глаголов, как to see, to look, ko'ymoq, qaramoq, которые классифицируются на основе таксономического подхода Ю.В.Падучевой (Т-категории). Также используется концептуально-таксономический метод анализа, разработанный Н.Н. Болдыревым, позволяющий определить иерархическую структуру концепта «визуальное восприятие». В статье представлены обязательные и факультативные признаки этого концепта, а также уровни и слои иерархии глаголов восприятия. Сравнительный анализ показывает как общие черты, так и различия в реализации глаголов визуального восприятия в английском и узбекском языках. Результаты исследования способствуют углубленному пониманию связи между языковыми единицами и когнитивными структурами.*

Ключевые слова: визуальное восприятие, таксономия глаголов, T-категории, семантика, когнитивная лингвистика, глаголы восприятия, концептуальный анализ, английский и узбекский языки, пропозициональная структура, активное/пассивное восприятие.

INTRODUCTION

Verbs related to visual perception in a general sense have long been the subject of study by numerous linguists. These language units have been examined within both structural linguistics and modern cognitive approaches. However, the issue of expressing the concept of visual perception through verbs has not been sufficiently explored, as the structure and description of the corresponding concept do not provide a complete representation of such a complex cognitive phenomenon as perception. Considering the functional grouping of visual perception verbs, a different cognitive modeling approach is required – one that may serve as a verbal taxonomic model of the concept of visual perception.

Taxonomy is a method of categorizing and hierarchically organizing objects, originally a concept from the field of biology. In linguistics, taxonomy is widely used to systematically classify linguistic phenomena. Specifically, linguistic units (such as parts of speech, syntactic constructions, or semantic categories) can be organized through hierarchical categorization. This approach simplifies the complex structure of the language system, making it easier to study and understand. For example, classifying verbs based on their meaning (action verbs, stative verbs, perception verbs, etc.) or their grammatical properties is carried out using taxonomic classification principles. A number of linguistic studies have traditionally applied this taxonomic method to systematically reveal relationships between lexical units and grammatical categories.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Russian linguist Y.Paducheva, in her research, applied the concept of taxonomic categories (which she sometimes refers to as T-categories) to classify linguistic meanings. Paducheva's work focuses on classifying verbs based on their semantic properties and grammatical behavior, and she referred to Vendler's aspectual classes of verbs as "taxonomic categories" due to their grammatical relevance [1]. That is, each verb belongs to a certain category in semantic classification, and this category is determined by its aspectual properties and its syntactic companions.

As Y.Paducheva notes, verbs are traditionally classified in two independent ways:

– **Thematically (ontologically)** — e.g., action verbs, state verbs, perception verbs, speech verbs, etc.

– **Aspectually** — following Vendler’s classification: states, processes, achievements, and punctual actions.

These two classifications are based on different principles and may function independently of each other. Paducheva’s approach is clearly exemplified through English perception verbs. In English, verbs that express sensation and perception – such as *to see*, *to hear*, *to look*, and *to listen* – differ semantically. Studies show that classifying these verbs into taxonomic categories helps explain the differences in their meanings and usage.

For example:

– *To see* and *to hear* represent **passive perception** (the process of perceiving an object occurs passively),

– While *to look (at)* and *to listen (to)* indicate **active perception** or an intentional act of observation (the subject’s attention is deliberately directed).

The T-categories described by Y.Paducheva clearly define the semantic classes of such verbs and serve to explain their grammatical characteristics. For example, the verb *to see* expresses a continuous state, which is why it is typically not used in progressive tense forms in English. In contrast, *to look*, which denotes an action, can freely appear in progressive constructions. This difference indicates that the two verbs belong to different taxonomic (aspectual) categories. Thus, Paducheva’s theory of T-categories explains the semantic nuances and grammatical behavior of English perception verbs through semantic classification.

The creation of a taxonomic model of the concept of visual perception verbs makes it possible to carry out conceptual-taxonomic analysis, as proposed and developed by N.N.Boldyrev. According to Boldyrev, conceptual-taxonomic analysis is a system of methods for studying the hierarchical structure of linguistic objects while taking into account the conceptual hierarchy – that is, the hierarchy of concepts expressed through those linguistic units.

RESULT

The use of conceptual-taxonomic analysis allows for the construction of a hierarchy of visual perception verbs in Uzbek and English, taking into account the conceptual features expressed by these verbs. The conceptual descriptions under consideration serve as elements of propositional structure, representing a specific format of knowledge about the state of visual perception. Among the core or obligatory features of the concept of visual perception that form the “nucleus” of the proposition are the characteristics of “subject,” “object,” and “direction.”

Along with the obligatory features of the concept “visual perception verb” in Uzbek and English, these verbs also have the capacity to express optional or additional features. These characteristics help specify and contextualize the

propositional structure of the verb. These optional features include: “time,” “manner” or “mode of seeing,” “obstacle,” “possibility of seeing,” “distance,” “holistic perception of the object,” “trajectory of gaze,” “cause,” “purpose,” and “accompanying activity.”

It should be emphasized that the taxonomic modeling of the concept of visual perception primarily aims to reflect the essence of perception as a phenomenon – on one hand, as an active and purposeful process (where the main goal is to obtain a specific visual image), and on the other hand, as passive seeing, which is unintentional and unconscious, involving the fixation and primary processing of visual stimuli arising from external sources.

Within the framework of the spoken taxonomy under investigation, two levels of classification are considered: the primary level and the subordinate level. The higher level can only be examined within the scope of the conceptual hierarchy of features, where it may be represented by a visual perception hyperconcept that generalizes the knowledge expressed at both the primary and subordinate levels.

However, despite the existence of this hyperconcept in the minds of Uzbek speakers, it is not lexically expressed. Therefore, within the structure of the taxonomy being analyzed, it is not observed at the linguistic level.

DISCUSSION

A hierarchy may also exist at an individual level. Accordingly, it seems reasonable to distinguish two layers within the primary level and three layers within the subordinate level. The classification of verbs into levels and layers is determined by their correspondence to general and specific criteria.

Following N.N. Boldyrev, we refer to the general criteria that allow for the grouping of verbs at the primary level, including:

- gestalt characteristics,
- morphological features,
- stylistic neutrality with wide verb combinability,
- and etymology (i.e., verbs at the primary level should historically belong to the core lexical fund of the given language).

According to N.N. Boldyrev, the general criteria for the subordinate level include the following:

- a) the verbs represent parts of a whole;
- b) they express narrow or specific features through words (in our case, this refers to a particular stage of the general process of visual perception);
- d) they are dependent;
- e) they result from derivation or synthesis (combination);
- f) they are considered substantives;

- g) they possess stylistic coloring;
- h) they belong to the category of neologisms or specialized vocabulary;
- i) they cannot function as phraseological units or independent sentence components [2].

The first layer of the primary level is represented by dominant verbs in the thematic group of non-purposeful and purposeful visual perception in English, such as *to see* and *to look*. In Uzbek, the visual cognitive verbs *ko'rmoq* (to see) and *qaramoq* (to look) serve as examples of this first layer.

In Uzbek, the most general and frequently used dominant verbs of visual perception are typically *ko'rmoq* and *qaramoq*. Semantically, these two verbs are closest to the English verbs *to see* (non-active, direct perception) and *to look* (active, intentional perception), respectively.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the analyses conducted reveal the connection between linguistic and conceptual levels. This relationship is significant not only within the framework of linguistics but also in broader cognitive contexts, providing a solid foundation for studying the reinterpretation of perceptual situations and their expression in various forms.

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